

OPTIMIZATION OF CLINOPTILOLITE TYPE ZEOLITE PARTICLE SIZES ON DIFFERENT NLGI GRADE LITHIUM SOAP GREASE FORMULATIONS

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ABSTRACT: Particle sizes of zeolites vary according to usage areas and needs. Zeolite ratios for required performance characteristics of lithium soap greases have been optimized in our previous study as 1%. In this study, we have been examined improvement of water resistance characteristic performance with using different size zeolites like: 10 µm, 40 µm, 100 µm and 700 µm. Three different NLGI grades lithium soaps have been used as: 00, 2 and 3. The zeolite size that showed highest water resistance performance was selected. Additionally, we have been reported that zeolites have been deteriorate extreme pressure performance characteristics of greases. Because of this reason we have been also studied with a commercial extreme pressure additive to increase load resistance performances of grease formulations. Appropriate size of zeolites type with optimized ratio used in studied formulations. And performance characteristics like: appearance, penetration, dropping point, NLGI no, wear scar, weld load, water spray and water washout have been reported.

KEYWORDS: Lubricant, lithium grease, clinoptilolite zeolite, water resistance, load resistance

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Solid Lubricants in Greases

Solid lubricants are common solutions for supporting of liquid lubricants and greases bearings that works under extreme operation conditions like high temperatures and pressures. [2]

General advantages of solid lubricants are: [4]

- Good stability under extreme conditions
- Changing thermal conductivity properties according to the base oil type
- Good resistance under environmental dirt
- Good chemical stability
- Good load carrying capability

General disadvantages of solid lubricants are: [4]

- Bad friction performance under hydrodynamic lubrication
- Changing thermal conductivity properties according to the base oil type
- Different colour according to solid lubricant type

It is widely known in grease industry that solid lubricants are used in extreme conditions, low speed boundary lubrication contact areas. [3]

1.2 Extreme Pressure Additives in Greases

Generally, both liquid lubricant and solid/semi-solid lubricant formulations have similar ingredients which are:

- Lubricant (which could be liquid, solid or semi-solid)
- Additives

Different types of additives can be used according to the lubricants' physical and chemical properties. Performance additive packages, corrosion inhibitors, extreme pressure additives, anti-wear additives, anti-foam additives, emulsifiers, metallic detergents, solid lubricants are some of the most used additive types in different types of lubricants.³ In this study we have been focused on especially load carrying improvement additives which are basically anti wear agents and extreme pressure additives [3]. Generally anti wear additives contains phosphorous derivatives [3]. Most used phosphorous derived anti wear additive molecules have been shown in figure-1-4. Figure 1

Figure 1. Structural form of metal dialkyl dithiophosphate

Figure 2. Structural form of tricresyl phosphate

Figure 3. Structural form of dialkyl phosphite

Figure 4. Structural form of phosphate

Generally extreme pressure additives contain sulphur and chlorine, etc [3]. Most used sulphur contain extreme pressure additives have been shown in figure-5-6.

Figure 5. Structural form of sulphurized fatty ester

Figure 6. Structural form of dibenzyl disulphide

Working mechanism of extreme pressure additives are well known in the lubrication industry. Basic most known mechanism is shown in following figure 7. In the working environment extreme pressure additives' molecules reacted with the surface of the contact material. This reaction is not started with contact. Increasing working temperature cause the reaction of extreme pressure additive molecules with contact surface material [4].

Figure 7. Working mechanism of extreme pressure additives

1.3. Zeolites

Zeolites are naturally abundant and synthetically produces inorganic, alkaline crystalline materials which are containing aluminium oxides, silicon oxides, hydrated aluminium silicates in their molecular structure [5][7][9][10]. Zeolites are generally using as catalysts in different applications, adsorbent material in different surfaces, detergent precursors and ion exchange materials in different environments [5][6]. Besides these areas there are lots of areas and applications where zeolites could be used. But it is also known that zeolites are good water absorbent/holding materials because of channels and tunnels in their molecular structure [10][6]. Crystalline structure of clinoptilolite zeolites include micropores to retain water in inner pores and secondary mesoporous to aeration and drainage [10].

He, Z.L et all [14] and Bigelow, C.A et all [15] reported that water absorbing capacity of different materials with different applications have been improved with using zeolites. Despite that according to our knowledge there is not any other study which used zeolites and clinoptilolite zeolites to improve the water adsorption properties of greases except our previous study reported by Sevda Şahan et all [16].

The term zeolite means boiling stone in Greek [7].

Clinoptilolite-which has an open formula $(\text{Na}_3\text{K}_3)(\text{Al}_6\text{Si}_{30}\text{O}_{72}) \cdot 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is one of the wide abundant types of natural zeolites [7][11][12][13]. According to M. C ulfaz et all [17] Si/Al ratio of clinoptilolite is between 4 and 5,5. Mostly it is used in environmental applications to absorb the toxic wastes and different medical applications. Besides that it is one of the well known properties of clinoptilolite zeolites that clinoptilolite zeolites adsorb the heavy metals in the working environment [7][8]. It is also known that cation exchange properties of clinoptilolite zeolites affected from the alkaline metal cations, chemical preparation methodology, physical preparation methodology, loading methodology and also regeneration type [18][19]. Common structural form of clinoptilolite type zeolites have been shown in figure 8.

Figure 8. Structural form of clinoptilolite type zeolites

1.4. Size Effect of Zeolites

There are different types of zeolites according to their molecular structure and their particle sizes. According to surface mechanics it is expected that to increasing the surface area of clinoptilolite zeolites as decreasing particle sizes. In case of zeolites, it should be expected that as decreasing particle sizes to increasing adsorption capacity [9].

According to A. R. Demirkiran et all [9]. differences in particle sizes of clinoptilolite zeolites showed different adsorption performances. And they also reported that oil adsorption of clinoptilolite type zeolites is higher at relatively lower temperatures like 500°C than higher temperatures like 700°C and 900°C [9]. In this study we have been attempting to investigate the size effect of clinoptilolite type zeolites on optimum usage ratio in lithium soap greases. Respectively 10 µm, 40 µm, 100 µm and 700 µm sized zeolites visual appearance has been shown in figure 8.

Figure 9. Visual appearance of different sized clinoptilolite zeolites

According to our knowledge there is not any commercial usage of clinoptilolite zeolites in greases. Lithium soap greases are one of the mostly used grease type in lubrication industry during long year. This could be attended on lithium soap greases' good performance characteristics.

Despite of their good performance characteristics in some application areas lithium soap greases required to improve their performance characteristics like water resistance and load resistance. In our previous study by Sevda Şahan et all [16]. we have been concluded that clinoptilolite type zeolites could be an alternative additive in spite of commercially known polymeric additives to improve greases' water resistance properties.

2. METHODOLOGY

At our previous study we have been reported that 1 % usage of clinoptilolite type zeolites is the optimum ratio to improve the water resistance performance properties of lithium soap greases. In this study consistency levels of used greases selected as NLGI 00, NLGI 2 and NLGI 3 grades.

As zeolite, we have been used clinoptilolite type zeolites based on our previous study. And to observe differences of performance effects of different sizes we have been selected and used 10 µm, 40 µm, 100 µm and 700 µm sized zeolites. All types of zeolites applied respectively 1 % ratio into different consistency level greases. Different characteristic test methodologies have been applied to observe performance properties of different sized zeolites in different consistency level lithium soap greases like: appearance, penetration, dropping point, NLGI no, wear scar, weld load, water spray and water washout.

2.1. Equipments and Test Methods

All performance analysis tested at POTEM. Consistency, 4 ball wear scar, 4 ball weld load, water spray off, water resistance, dropping point analysis of synthesized greases have been reported. Consistency test applied according to ASTM D217 test standard. 4 ball wear scar test applied according to ASTM D2266 test standard. Weld load test applied according to ASTM D2596 test standard. Water spray off test applied according to ASTM D4049 test standard. Water resistance test applied according to ASTM D1264 test standard. Dropping point test applied according to ASTM D566 test standard.

2.2. Tables and Figures

Different NLGI grade lithium greases' formulation details have been shown for NLGI 00 grade in table-1, for NLGI 2 grade in table-2 and for NLGI 3 grade in table-3.

Table-1. Formulation detail of NLGI 00 grade lithium greases

FORMULATION, % WEIGHT	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C5-EP
Lithium soap grease formulation NLGI 00 level	100	99	99	99	99	
Zeolite 10µm		1				
Zeolite 40µm			1			
Zeolite 100µm				1		
Zeolite 700µm					1	

Formulation C5						95
EP/AW Additive						5

Table-2. Formulation detail of NLGI 2 grade lithium greases

FORMULATION, % WEIGHT	B1	B2	B3	B4	B5	B5-EP
Lithium soap grease formulation NLGI 2level	100	99	99	99	99	
Zeolite 10µm		1				
Zeolite 40µm			1			
Zeolite 100µm				1		
Zeolite 700µm					1	
Formulation B5						95
EP/AW Additive						5

Table-3. Formulation detail of NLGI 3 grade lithium greases

FORMULATION, % WEIGHT	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A5-EP
Lithium soap grease formulation NLGI 3 level	100	99	99	99	99	
Zeolite 10µm		1				
Zeolite 40µm			1			
Zeolite 100µm				1		
Zeolite 700µm					1	
Formulation A5						95
EP/AW Additive						5

Visual appearance of NLGI 3 grade lithium soap formulations have been shown in figure-10.

Figure 10. Visual appearances of NLGI 3 grade lithium soap formulations

Visual appearance of NLGI 2 grade lithium soap formulations have been shown in figure-10.

Figure 11. Visual appearances of NLGI 2 grade lithium soap formulations

Visual appearance of NLGI 00 grade lithium soap formulations have been shown in figure-10.

Figure 12. Visual appearances of NLGI 00 grade lithium soap formulations

Consistency test results of different NLGI grade grease formulations have been shown in figure 13.

Figure 13. Penetration test results of grease formulations

Dropping point test results of different NLGI grade grease formulations have been shown in figure 14.

Figure 14. Dropping point test results of grease formulations

Wear scar test results of different NLGI grade grease formulations have been shown in figure 15.

Figure 15. Wear scar test results of grease formulations

Besides that, four ball wear scar visuals of different grease formulations have been shown in figure 16-17-18.

Figure 16. 4 ball wear scar visuals of NLGI 3 grade lithium soap formulations

Figure 17. 4 ball wear scar visuals of NLGI 2 grade lithium soap formulations

Figure 18. 4 ball wear scar visuals of NLGI 00 grade lithium soap formulations

Four ball weld load test results of different NLGI grade grease formulations have been shown in figure 19.

Figure 19. Four ball weld load test results of grease formulations

Water washout test results of different NLGI grade grease formulations have been shown in figure 20.

Figure 20. Water washout test results of grease formulations

Water spray off test results of different NLGI grade grease formulations have been shown in figure 21.

Figure 21. Water spray off test results of grease formulations

3. DISCUSSION

It has been shown that 1 % ratio of clinoptilolite zeolites is the optimum ratio for usage in lithium soap greases.

Different sizes of clinoptilolite zeolites are not significantly affected to the visual appearances of NLGI 00, NLGI 2 and NLGI 3 grades lithium soap greases.

Penetration values of greases have been effected by different particle sizes but NLGI grades did not change.

Dropping point values of different grade greases with different size clinoptilolite zeolites changed. But reported changes in results could commented like between reproducibility area in the standard test method.

According to load carrying analysis results;

Wear scar analysis results of NLGI 00, NLGI 2 and NLGI 3 grade lithium grease increased with addition of zeolites. According to the test results it has been seen that addition of a commercial extreme pressure additive package could eliminate significantly the wear scar increase with zeolite addition. It has been also observed that smaller particle size of zeolites tend to increase wear scar of lithium based greases. This phenomenon could attributed the higher surface area of smaller particle sized zeolites. Four ball weld load test results were compatible with this results. Weld load of grease is one grade higher than grease with zeolite. According to the test results it has been shown that addition of a commercial extreme pressure additive package could eliminate significantly the weld load decrease with zeolite addition. Increasing wear scar and decreasing weld load performance characteristics could be attributed to the small solid structural characteristics of zeolites. Because of this structure zeolite particles could harm the surface without extreme pressure additives.

According to test results did not change significantly for NLGI 2 and NLGI 3 grade greases. Despite that is has been reported that water washout test results increased with increasing zeolite sizes in NLGI 00 grade lithium greases. This phenomenon could be attributed to the very thin and low ratio of soap of this kind of low consistency formulations. This could be commented as zeolite usage to improve water resistance properties lower consistency level grade lithium greases could not an appropriate choice.

According to water spray off test results it has been reported that increasing zeolite particle size effected better to the water resistance performance of all three grade lithium soap greases. Additionally, according to these results it has been seen that clinoptilolite type zeolites and commercial extreme pressure additives shows synergistic performance on both water washout and water spray off performance results.

4. FINDINGS

In this study all blends, reactions and analysis have been performed in Petrol Ofisi Group Technology Center (POTEM) Laboratory. All supplies that used in this study produced by Petrol Ofisi Group. We have been divided the experimental design onto two steps in this study.

At the step 1; we have been investigated the optimum particle size for usage in different grades of lithium soap greases.

At the step 2; we have been investigated the final product performance characteristics with using extreme pressure additive package beside clinoptilolite type zeolites.

According to the results of step 1;

At our previous study we have been reported that 1 % usage of clinoptilolite type zeolites is the optimum ratio to improve the water resistance properties of lithium soap greases which have been published by Sevda Şahan et all [16].

NLGI 00, NLGI 2 and NLGI 3 grade lithium soap greases have been used in this study.

According to visual appearance examinations addition of clinoptilolite type zeolites did not effect significantly on the color and visual appearance of greases. Changing particle size of zeolites did not affected significantly on the visual appearances of NLGI 00, NLGI 2 and NLGI 3 greases.

NLGI 3 grade lithium soap grease;

At step 1:

It has been seen that penetration value increase with increasing zeolite size. Despite that NLGI number of grease samples did not change.

It has been seen that dropping point of the grease did not change significantly with different sized chlinoptilolite zeolites.

According to analysis results four ball wear scar of NLGI 3 grade lithium soap grease increased with addition of zeolites. Wear scar sizes were higher with 10 μm and 40 μm sized zeolites than 100 μm and 700 μm sized zeolites.

It has been seen that water washout test results did not change significantly. Changes in water washout test results in between repeatability and reproducibility area of the standard test method.

According to water spray off test results we have been reported that water spray off performance of calcium soap NLGI 3 grade greases improved about 2,5 % ratio with 10 μm and 40 μm sized zeolites, about 8 % ratio with 100 μm sized zeolites and about 8 % ratio with 10 μm sized zeolites.

At step 2:

It has been seen that penetration value increase with addition of EP additive package. Despite that NLGI number of grease samples did not change.

It has been seen that dropping point of the grease did not change significantly with addition EP additive package. Reported changes in results could be commented like between reproducibility area in the standard test method.

According to analysis results four ball wear scar of NLGI 3 grade lithium soap grease showed small decrease with addition of EP additive package. Four ball load of grease is reported as two grade higher.

It has been seen that water washout test results did not change significantly. Changes in water washout test results in between repeatability and reproducibility area of the standard test method.

According to water spray off test results we have been reported that water spray off performance of calcium soap NLGI 3 grade greases improved about 30 % ratio with 700 μm sized zeolites. It has been seen that EP additive package and zeolites have synergistic effect in water spray off performance.

NLGI 2 grade lithium soap grease;

At step 1:

It has been seen that penetration value increase with increasing zeolite size. Despite that NLGI number of grease samples did not change.

It has been seen that dropping point of the grease did not change significantly with different sized chlinoptilolite zeolites.

According to analysis results four ball wear scar of NLGI 2 grade lithium soap grease increased with addition of zeolites. Wear scar size test results were similar in between reproducibility interval of the standard test method.

It has been seen that water washout test results of greases with 10 μm and 40 μm sized zeolites improved about 2 % and 4 % ratios.

According to water spray off test results we have been reported that water spray off performance of calcium soap NLGI 2 grade greases improved about 2,5 % ratio with 10 μm and 40 μm sized zeolites, about 8 % ratio with 100 μm sized zeolites and about 8 % ratio with 700 μm sized zeolites.

At step 2:

It has been seen that penetration value increase with addition of EP additive package. Despite that NLGI number of grease samples did not change.

It has been seen that dropping point of the grease did not change significantly with addition EP additive package. Reported changes in results could commented like between reproducibility area in the standard test method.

According to analysis results four ball wear scar of NLGI 2 grade lithium soap grease showed small decrease with addition of EP additive package. Four ball weld load of grease is reported as one grade higher.

It has been seen that water washout test results did not change significantly. Changes in water washout test results in between repeatability and reproducibility area of the standard test method.

According to water spray off test results we have been reported that water spray off performance of calcium soap NLGI 2 grade greases improved about 5 % ratio with 700 μm sized zeolites. It has been seen that EP additive package and zeolites have synergistic effect in water spray off performance.

NLGI 00 grade lithium soap grease;

At step 1:

It has been seen that penetration value increase with increasing zeolite size. Despite that NLGI number of grease samples did not change.

It has been seen that dropping point of the grease did not change significantly with different sized chlinotilolite zeolites.

According to analysis results four ball wear scar of NLGI 00 grade lithium soap grease increased with addition of zeolites. Weld load of grease is one grade higher than grease with zeolite.

It has been seen that water washout test results of greases with 10 μm sized zeolites increased about 2 % ratio, with 40 μm sized zeolites increased about 8 % ratio, with 100 μm sized zeolites increased about 10 % ratio and with 700 μm sized zeolites increased about 12 % ratio. Despite that, it has been seen that water spray off test results of greases with 10 μm sized zeolites increased about 4 % ratio, with 40 μm sized zeolites increased about 5 % ratio, with 100 μm sized zeolites increased about 5 % ratio and with 700 μm sized zeolites increased about 6 % ratio.

At step 2:

It has been seen that penetration value increase with addition of EP additive package. Despite that NLGI number of grease samples did not change.

It has been seen that dropping point of the grease did not change significantly with addition EP additive package. Reported changes in results could commented like between reproducibility area in the standard test method.

According to analysis results four ball wear scar of NLGI 00 grade lithium soap grease showed small decrease with addition of EP additive package. Four ball weld load of grease is reported as one grade higher.

It has been seen that water washout test results improved about 11% ratio with 700 μm sized zeolites and with addition of EP additive package.

According to water spray off test results we have been reported that water spray off performance of calcium soap NLGI 00 grade greases improved about 2 % ratio with 700 μm sized zeolites. It has been seen that EP additive package and zeolites have synergistic effect in water spray off performance.

5. CONCLUSION

As a conclusion;

Usage of clinoptilolite type zeolite could be an alternative to usage of traditional polymeric water resistance additives in greases.

Different particle sizes of zeolites affect differently on performance characteristics of greases.

Zeolites could deteriorate the extreme pressure performance characteristics of greases. Despite that addition of a commercial extreme pressure additive could eliminate this deterioration and synergistic effect of zeolites and extreme pressure additives on performance characteristics of lithium greases have been reported.

Performance increasing effect of zeolite particles could not be seen with lower NLGI grade greases like NLGI 00 grade because of extremely lower consistency and more liquid like natures of these products.

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